

The preparedness gap in German households: A quantitative analysis of perceived and objective disaster preparedness

Author:

Fabian Erik Schmidt

Affiliation:

Master's Program in Crisis and Emergency Management, Hochschule Fresenius, Germany

Acknowledgements

This study was conducted as part of an academic examination requirement. Data analysis and manuscript preparation were carried out independently by the author.

Declaration of competing interests

The author declares that he has no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Declaration of AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

AI-based tools were used for language editing and stylistic refinement only. The authors retain full responsibility for the content of the manuscript.

Funding

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Ethics statement

The study was conducted in accordance with ethical standards for social science research. Participation was voluntary and anonymous, and informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection. No sensitive personal data were collected. Ethical approval was not required under national regulations for anonymous survey research.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

10.5281/zenodo.18680401

Abstract

Household preparedness is widely recognized as a core component of disaster risk reduction, particularly during the early phase of crises when external assistance may be delayed. However, empirical evidence suggests that individuals' subjective assessments of preparedness do not necessarily correspond to objectively measurable household capacities. This study examines the extent of discrepancies between perceived and objective preparedness and investigates sociodemographic, experiential, and psychological factors associated with objective household preparedness in Germany.

Data were collected through a cross-sectional online survey (n = 266). Objective preparedness was operationalized using a resource-based household index capturing tangible preparedness components relevant during short-term disruptions. Discrepancies between perceived and objective preparedness were used to identify over- and underestimation patterns. Analyses included descriptive statistics, correlation analyses, and hierarchical linear regression models.

Results indicate that more than half of participants misjudged their level of preparedness, with substantial proportions either overestimating or underestimating their actual preparedness. Objective preparedness was only partly explained by sociodemographic characteristics and crisis experience. Psychological factors related to perceived self-efficacy, responsibility attribution, and reliance on authorities showed additional associations with objective preparedness.

The findings demonstrate that subjective preparedness is a poor proxy for actual household preparedness. From a disaster risk science perspective, the results highlight the importance of implementation-related psychological factors for translating awareness into tangible preparedness capacities and provide implications for improving preparedness communication within disaster risk reduction frameworks.

Keywords

household preparedness; disaster risk reduction; risk perception; self-efficacy; miscalibration; resilience; Germany

1 Introduction

Large-scale disruptions of critical infrastructures, extreme weather events, pandemics, and evolving security threats have underscored the vulnerability of modern societies, even in highly developed countries (United Nations Office for Disaster Risk, 2022). Recent crises, including prolonged power outages, regional flooding, heatwaves with severe health impacts, supply chain disruptions during the COVID-19 pandemic, and the reassessment of hybrid threats, demonstrate that public protection and response systems can reach operational and temporal limits during acute and wide-ranging emergencies (OECD, 2025). In such situations, the short-term self-help capacity of private households becomes a critical factor for societal functioning and system stability.

In disaster risk reduction research, resilience is not conceptualized as mere robustness, but as a system's ability to anticipate disturbances, absorb shocks, maintain core functions, and adapt after disruptive events. Importantly, resilience does not emerge solely from technical redundancy or institutional capacities, but from interactions across multiple levels, including public authorities, critical infrastructures, communities, and households (Norris et al., 2008; United Nations Office for Disaster Risk, 2022). At the household level, resilience primarily refers to short-term preparedness and self-help capacity, defined as the ability to remain functional during the initial hours and days of a crisis without immediate external assistance (Mileti et al., 1992; Tierney, 2002). This level is operationally critical, as it bridges the time gap until public response mechanisms can be fully mobilized.

The all-hazards approach, which underpins many national and international civil protection strategies, emphasizes that different hazards often generate similar functional demands, such as access to information, supply security, mobility, health protection, and social support (OECD, 2025; United Nations Office for Disaster Risk, 2022). Household preparedness therefore does not primarily target specific scenarios, but rather resources and capacities that are effective across multiple types of crises. This perspective is particularly relevant under conditions of uncertainty, where cascading effects across critical infrastructures, such as those triggered by power outages, can amplify initial disruptions (Helbing, 2013; Pescaroli and Alexander, 2015).

Importantly, individual preparedness should not be interpreted as a transfer of responsibility from the state to citizens (Boin and Lodge, 2016; OECD, 2025). Public authorities remain primarily responsible for hazard prevention, protection of critical infrastructures, warning, rescue, and emergency response. However, modern disaster governance is based on a division of labor, recognizing that public systems cannot provide immediate and comprehensive support in all scenarios, especially during large-scale or prolonged events. Household self-

help capacity thus functions as a complementary buffer rather than a substitute for state action. This creates a central challenge for civil protection: promoting individual preparedness without undermining state responsibility or exacerbating social inequalities.

Against this backdrop, national and international institutions have long recommended that households implement basic preparedness measures. In Germany, the Federal Office of Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance (BBK) advises households to stock water, food, and medications and to maintain independent information and communication tools to ensure self-sufficiency for several days. While preparedness targets of up to ten days are discussed, even a three-day supply is considered a realistic minimum (BBK, 2025). Similar recommendations are increasingly articulated at the European level, where a minimum of 72 hours of household self-sufficiency is framed as a core component of societal resilience (BBK, 2025).

Despite these recommendations, empirical studies consistently show that actual household preparedness remains below these targets. National surveys and large-scale assessments by civil protection agencies and humanitarian organizations report that while basic everyday resources are common, more systematic or crisis-specific preparedness measures are comparatively rare (Gerhold et al., 2019). These findings are often described descriptively as deficits, but provide limited insight into why households fail to translate recommendations, crisis experience, and risk awareness into concrete preparedness actions (Bubeck et al., 2012; Wachinger et al., 2013).

Recent research increasingly suggests that preparedness is shaped by discrepancies between perceived preparedness, risk perception, and objectively measurable resources. In the international literature, this phenomenon has been described as a “disaster preparedness gap” or “readiness gap,” indicating systematic mismatches between subjective assessments and actual preparedness levels (Gowan et al., 2015; Paton, 2003). Such miscalibration is particularly relevant for disaster risk reduction, as subjective perceptions often guide everyday decision-making and may either trigger or inhibit preparedness behavior.

The concept of preparedness itself remains contested, encompassing resource-based, behavioral, and capability-oriented dimensions depending on theoretical perspective. In this study, a resource-based index of objective preparedness was deliberately chosen (Mileti et al., 1992; Tierney, 2002). First, material and organizational resources constitute a necessary precondition for short-term household self-help and are directly aligned with national and European preparedness guidelines (BBK, 2025). Second, resource-based indicators allow for standardized and comparatively valid measurement in online surveys, whereas behavioral or performance-based assessments of crisis response capacities pose substantial methodological challenges (Cutter et al., 2008; Norris et al., 2008).

For Germany, empirical evidence on the alignment between subjective preparedness and objective household resources remains limited. Qualitative studies at the community level

reveal that citizens generally perceive preparedness as important, yet frequently report uncertainty, cognitive overload, and practical barriers to implementation (Lacher, 2024; Wachinger et al., 2013). However, such studies cannot determine the extent to which subjective preparedness assessments correspond to actual household readiness or identify systematic determinants of miscalibration.

Quantitative studies, in turn, often focus either on the prevalence of specific preparedness measures or on risk perception and attitudes, without explicitly linking subjective assessments to objective preparedness indicators (Bubeck et al., 2012; Gerhold et al., 2019). As a result, little is known about how socio-demographic characteristics, residential context, personal crisis experience, psychological factors such as self-efficacy or avoidance, and trust in institutions jointly shape preparedness and preparedness miscalibration (Grothmann and Reusswig, 2006; Paton, 2003).

Recent representative surveys in Germany further indicate that preparedness is strongly stratified by education, income, and institutional embeddedness (Rohs et al., 2025), while qualitative analyses highlight barriers such as fear, lack of routines, and limited agency, particularly among socioeconomically disadvantaged groups (Lacher et al., 2025). These findings suggest that insufficient preparedness may be less a matter of awareness than of structural and psychological constraints.

From a disaster risk reduction perspective, the calibration of subjective preparedness assessments is therefore of central importance. Overestimation of preparedness may reduce motivation for further action, while underestimation may foster uncertainty, avoidance, or inefficient prioritization (Grothmann and Reusswig, 2006; Wachinger et al., 2013). Preparedness gaps thus represent not merely a measurement issue, but a practical challenge for risk governance, as subjective perceptions function as heuristics that shape preparedness decisions in everyday life (Bubeck et al., 2012; Paton, 2003).

Against this background, the study focuses on a concrete empirical question: whether individuals' self-assessments of preparedness correspond to the resources actually available at the household level, and which factors systematically shape potential discrepancies. By explicitly linking subjective perceptions with objective indicators, the study moves beyond normative assessments of preparedness deficits toward a differentiated analysis of the conditions under which household preparedness emerges, fails, or is misperceived (Norris et al., 2008; Paton, 2003).

The central research question is therefore:

Does a preparedness gap exist, and which factors determine individual household preparedness?

In addition, the study examines whether preparedness varies by age, education, income, and residential context, including potential differences between urban and rural settings (Bubeck

et al., 2012; Gerhold et al., 2019). These hypotheses are not treated as assumptions but are empirically tested within a comprehensive analytical framework.

1.1 Definition of the Preparedness Gap

In this study, the preparedness gap is operationally defined as a systematic discrepancy between (a) subjective assessments of individual preparedness for crises and disasters and (b) objectively measured household preparedness based on concrete, verifiable resources and measures (Gowan et al., 2015). Following international discussions of the disaster preparedness gap, respondents are categorized as overestimating, underestimating, or realistically assessing their preparedness (Gowan et al., 2015; Paton, 2003). This approach allows preparedness to be examined not only as a matter of resource availability, but as a relationship between perception and implementation, distinguishing systematic over- and underestimation from realistic self-assessment (Wachinger et al., 2013).

2 Study design and objectives

This study employed a quantitative, cross-sectional survey design to examine the existence and determinants of a preparedness gap at the individual household level. Rather than evaluating preparedness for isolated hazard scenarios, the study focused on systematically assessing discrepancies between subjective preparedness assessments and objectively measured household preparedness. In addition, socio-demographic, experiential, and psychological factors associated with individual preparedness were analyzed.

The design was chosen to enable both descriptive analyses of household preparedness levels and inferential statistical analyses to explain individual differences in preparedness. By integrating subjective and objective indicators, the study adopts an analytical approach that extends beyond purely descriptive preparedness assessments commonly used in disaster research.

2.1 Data collection

Data were collected through a standardized online survey administered via the EU Survey platform. The online format enabled time- and location-independent participation and facilitated access to diverse population groups. At the same time, it is acknowledged that online surveys may involve an increased risk of thematic self-selection (see Section 5 on limitations).

The survey was conducted between 14 November and 31 December 2025. Prior to data collection, the questionnaire was reviewed for clarity, logical structure, and technical functionality. Participation was voluntary and anonymous. No personally identifiable information was collected that would allow identification of individual respondents.

2.2 Sample and recruitment

Participants were recruited through multiple channels to achieve a heterogeneous sample. Recruitment strategies included dissemination through private and professional networks, promotion via social media platforms, and targeted outreach to institutions and organizations. Municipal authorities (e.g., local citizen offices) were contacted and asked to display study flyers. In addition, organizations and networks related to civil protection and civil society, including professional associations and aid organizations, supported dissemination through their communication channels.

This multi-channel recruitment strategy aimed to reach both individuals with heightened interest in crisis preparedness and respondents without direct institutional ties to civil protection structures. Nevertheless, the resulting sample is non-representative, and this limitation is explicitly considered in the interpretation of results.

Gender was assessed via self-identification with the response options male, female, and diverse. Gender was treated as a sociodemographic variable in descriptive and exploratory analyses.

2.3 Questionnaire structure and measures

The questionnaire was theory-driven and structured in modular sections. This design allowed different dimensions of household preparedness to be assessed separately while maintaining conceptual coherence. The sequence of modules followed a logical progression from subjective perceptions to concrete preparedness measures to minimize potential priming effects.

2.4 Subjective preparedness and risk perception

Participants were first asked to assess their subjective preparedness for crises and disasters. This assessment was conducted independently of any questions regarding specific resources or measures and formed the basis for identifying preparedness miscalibration. Additionally, respondents evaluated the perceived likelihood of several crisis scenarios (e.g., prolonged power outage, extreme weather, pandemic), enabling analysis of relationships between risk perception and subjective preparedness.

2.5 Objective preparedness: household resources and measures

Objective household preparedness was assessed using concrete, verifiable preparedness measures. Item selection was guided by national preparedness recommendations and included:

- material resources (e.g., water, food supplies, medications),
- information and communication resources (e.g., flashlight, radio),
- organizational measures (e.g., emergency or evacuation bag).

Items were predominantly measured dichotomously (present vs. not present) and aggregated into an index of objective preparedness. This operationalization provided a standardized measure of household-level preparedness independent of subjective self-assessments.

2.6 Preparedness gap

The preparedness gap was operationalized as the discrepancy between subjective preparedness and objectively assessed household preparedness. Subjective preparedness was measured using a Likert-scale item assessing respondents perceived level of preparedness, while objective preparedness was represented by a resource-based index aggregating the availability of key preparedness resources.

To enable an interpretable classification of miscalibration patterns, both subjective preparedness scores and the objective preparedness index were standardized (z-scores). The preparedness gap was then calculated as the difference between standardized subjective preparedness and standardized objective preparedness.

Based on this difference score, participants were categorized into three groups:

- Overestimation of preparedness: subjective preparedness exceeding objective preparedness by more than 0.5 standard deviations
- Underestimation of preparedness: subjective preparedness falling below objective preparedness by more than 0.5 standard deviations
- Realistic assessment: subjective and objective preparedness differing by no more than ± 0.5 standard deviations

The threshold of ± 0.5 standard deviations was chosen to balance sensitivity and robustness. This cut-off allows for the identification of substantively relevant miscalibration while avoiding overclassification due to minor measurement noise or scale-related variability. Similar tolerance-based approaches have been applied in prior research on preparedness calibration and risk perception discrepancies (e.g., Gowan et al., 2015).

The classification does not define normative standards of ‘adequate’ preparedness but serves to identify systematic patterns of misalignment between perceived and observable preparedness.

2.7 Psychological variables and attitudes

Several psychological constructs relevant to preparedness behavior were assessed, including self-efficacy, action orientation, avoidance tendencies, perceived overload from crisis-related information, and attitudes toward individual versus state responsibility. Items were formulated as statements and rated using multi-point Likert scales.

Selection of these variables was informed by established models of risk perception and protective action, which emphasize that preparedness behavior is shaped not only by knowledge or perceived risk, but also by perceived coping capacity and emotional processing.

2.8 Socio-demographic and experiential variables

Socio-demographic characteristics (including age, gender, education, income, and residential context) and self-reported personal experience with crisis events were collected. These variables served both descriptive purposes and as potential predictors of objective preparedness and preparedness miscalibration.

2.9 Processing and statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were conducted using jamovi (version 2.7.6.0). Descriptive statistics (means, standard deviations, and frequencies) were calculated to summarize key variables.

Group differences in objective preparedness were examined using one-way analyses of variance (ANOVA), particularly with respect to residential context. Assumptions of linear regression (normality of residuals, homoscedasticity, and multicollinearity) were assessed and met at acceptable levels.

Associations between variables were analyzed using correlation analyses. To identify determinants of objective preparedness, multiple linear regression analyses were conducted. Regression models were built hierarchically, first including socio-demographic variables and subsequently adding experiential and psychological factors to assess incremental explanatory power.

2.10 Ethics and data protection

The study was conducted in accordance with fundamental ethical principles of social science research. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to participation.

All data were collected in anonymized form. The survey did not include any information that would allow direct or indirect identification of participants. No names, addresses, IP addresses, or other personal identifiers were stored. Data were collected exclusively for scientific purposes.

Data collection was conducted via the EU Survey platform, which complies with European Union data protection standards. Data processing adhered to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Access to raw data was restricted to the authors of the study.

As the study involved an anonymous, non-interventional survey without sensitive personal data and posed no health or psychological risks to participants, formal approval by an ethics committee was not required under applicable ethical guidelines. Nevertheless, principles of transparency, proportionality, and purpose limitation were strictly observed.

3 Results

3.1 Sample characteristics

A total of 266 participants completed the online survey. Mean age was 38.8 years (SD = 14.5; n = 265). Regarding gender, 51.9% identified as male, 47.0% as female, and 1.1% as diverse.

The highest educational attainment (n = 265) was distributed as follows: 44.2% reported a university degree and 31.7% reported a higher education entrance qualification (Abitur or equivalent).

Monthly net household income was reported by n = 263 participants. 33.1% indicated a household income above €5,000 per month.

With respect to place of residence, 26.4% lived in rural communities (<5,000 inhabitants), 19.2% in small towns, 17.4% in medium-sized cities, and 37.0% in large cities (>100,000 inhabitants).

Table 1-4 summarizes the key sociodemographic characteristics of the sample. Additional descriptive details are provided in the supplementary material.

3.2 Subjective preparedness and scenario-specific risk perceptions

Participants' overall subjective assessment of being prepared for a major crisis yielded a mean score of $M = 2.87$ (SD = 1.01; n = 260).

Scenario-specific assessments showed the following mean values for perceived likelihood and self-assessed preparedness:

- Long-term power outage: perceived likelihood $M = 3.35$ (SD = 1.13; n = 261); self-assessed preparedness $M = 2.72$ (SD = 1.12; n = 261).
- Natural disasters: perceived likelihood $M = 3.16$ (SD = 1.19; n = 261); self-assessed preparedness $M = 2.60$ (SD = 1.01; n = 261).
- Supply shortages: perceived likelihood $M = 3.27$ (SD = 1.12; n = 262); self-assessed preparedness $M = 2.62$ (SD = 1.09; n = 262).
- Pandemic or health crisis: perceived likelihood $M = 3.66$ (SD = 1.13; n = 260); self-assessed preparedness $M = 2.99$ (SD = 1.01; n = 260).

Descriptive results on subjective preparedness and scenario-specific risk perceptions are summarized in Table 5.

3.3 Psychological and social variables

Mean values for psychological (Table 6) and social (Table 7) variables are summarized. Perceived ability to remain capable of action in a crisis yielded a mean score of $M = 3.71$ ($SD = 1.11$; $n = 266$), while perceived problem-solving capability showed a mean of $M = 3.94$ ($SD = 1.07$; $n = 266$).

Perceived ability to protect one's household in an emergency was rated at $M = 3.15$ ($SD = 1.12$; $n = 266$). Agreement with statements reflecting optimism bias ("disasters usually affect others") showed a mean of $M = 2.29$ ($SD = 1.24$; $n = 266$).

Responsibility attribution to oneself for preparedness yielded $M = 3.73$ ($SD = 1.24$; $n = 266$), whereas attribution of responsibility to public authorities yielded $M = 2.36$ ($SD = 1.18$; $n = 266$).

3.4 Objective preparedness: household-level resources

Objective preparedness was assessed using a resource-based index composed of concrete household-level preparedness measures. Frequencies of individual preparedness components are shown in Table 8.

The most frequently reported resources were alternative light sources (96.6%), emergency medication supplies (90.2%), and food supplies for at least three days (81.2%). Lower frequencies were observed for water reserves meeting recommended thresholds (62.3%), availability of a battery-powered radio (40.0%), and a prepared evacuation bag (10.5%).

The aggregated objective preparedness index showed a mean value of $M = 0.58$ ($SD = 0.18$).

3.5 Preparedness gap

Preparedness gap categories could be calculated for $n = 249$ participants. 45.0% showed a realistic alignment between subjective and objective preparedness. 28.5% overestimated and 26.5% underestimated their level of preparedness.

The distribution of preparedness gap categories across age groups is displayed in Figure 1.

3.6 Reported reasons for insufficient household preparedness

Participants who indicated insufficient preparedness were asked to select reasons that hindered implementation (multiple selections possible). The most frequently endorsed reasons were "I have not thought about it yet" ($n = 80$; 30.1%), "I do not know where to start" ($n = 75$; 28.2%), and "I do not have the money for it" ($n = 75$; 28.2%). Time constraints were also common ("I do not have time": $n = 60$; 22.6%). A minority selected "Nothing will happen anyway" ($n = 28$; 10.5%). A detailed overview is provided in Table 9.

3.7 Trust in information sources for warnings during a crisis

Participants were asked which actors and channels they would trust for warnings and crisis-related information (multiple selections possible). Trust was highest for emergency response organizations: fire services were selected by 85.0% (n = 226) and emergency medical services by 72.6% (n = 193). Public authorities were selected by 63.2% (n = 168), and government sources by 52.3% (n = 139).

Traditional mass media were mentioned less frequently (radio: 42.5%, n = 113; television: 30.5%, n = 81). Informal social sources were endorsed by about one quarter (family: 24.4%, n = 65; friends: 18.8%, n = 50). Social media were rarely selected as a trusted warning source (7.9%, n = 21).

3.8 Use of information sources for crisis and security-related topics

Participants were asked which channels they usually use to inform themselves about crisis and security-related topics (multiple selections possible). The most frequently used sources were official channels and warning apps (e.g., NINA, KATWARN), endorsed by 72.9% (n = 194). Traditional media remained relevant: television was selected by 45.1% (n = 120) and radio by 37.6% (n = 100). Social media were used by 32.3% (n = 86). Friends/family were less frequently mentioned (23.3%, n = 62).

3.9 Objective preparedness by municipality size

Objective preparedness did not differ significantly by municipality size (Welch's ANOVA: $F(3,121) = 1.49$, $p = 0.221$). Mean values of the preparedness index ranged from $M = 0.556$ ($SD = 0.182$) in large cities to $M = 0.615$ ($SD = 0.175$) in rural communities. No significant pairwise differences were observed in post-hoc tests.

3.10 Bivariate associations with objective preparedness

3.10.1 Sociodemographic variables

Spearman correlation analyses revealed significant positive associations between objective preparedness and age ($\rho = 0.24$, $p < 0.001$), educational attainment ($\rho = 0.19$, $p = 0.002$), and household income ($\rho = 0.31$, $p < 0.001$). Gender showed a significant association ($\rho = -0.28$, $p < 0.001$). No significant associations were observed for place of residence or household composition.

3.10.2 Crisis experience

Personal experience with crisis events was positively associated with objective preparedness ($\rho = 0.17$, $p = 0.008$). No significant association was found between crisis experience and preparedness gap categories.

3.10.3 Psychological variables

Objective preparedness was positively associated with perceived action capability ($\rho = 0.23$, $p < 0.001$), problem-solving beliefs ($\rho = 0.28$, $p < 0.001$), and personal responsibility attribution ($\rho = 0.22$, $p < 0.001$). Negative associations were observed for avoidance-oriented and externalizing attitudes.

3.11 Multivariate prediction of objective preparedness

Hierarchical linear regression analyses were conducted for 249 participants to examine predictors of objective household preparedness. In the sociodemographic model, age and educational attainment were positively associated with preparedness, while gender showed no significant effect. Overall, sociodemographic variables explained 28.6% of the variance in objective preparedness ($R^2 = 0.286$). Although gender showed a significant bivariate association with objective preparedness, this effect did not remain significant after adjustment for age and educational attainment in the multivariable model.

The inclusion of psychological and experience-related variables in the second model significantly improved model fit, increasing explained variance to 41.1% ($\Delta R^2 = 0.125$; F-change (17,213) = 2.66, $p < 0.001$). In the fully adjusted model, age remained a robust predictor of preparedness. In addition, the belief that one's preparation would be sufficient in a real disaster showed a strong and independent association with objective preparedness. Educational effects were attenuated but remained directionally consistent. Neither gender nor prior crisis experience reached statistical significance in the final model.

Additional descriptive statistics, correlation analyses, and intermediate regression models are provided in the supplementary material.

4 Discussion

4.1 What this study shows about household preparedness

This study addressed a simple but consequential question: do people who consider themselves prepared for crises possess the household-level resources needed for short-term self-help, and what explains systematic mismatches between perception and reality? The results point to three central findings.

First, miscalibration between perceived and objective preparedness is widespread. Less than half of participants showed a realistic alignment between self-assessment and resource-based preparedness, while substantial proportions either overestimated (28.5%) or underestimated (26.5%) their preparedness. Second, objective preparedness did not differ meaningfully across municipality-size categories, suggesting that common urban vs. rural distinctions provide limited explanatory value in this context. Third, preparedness was shaped by a combination of sociodemographic and psychological factors, with capability-related beliefs adding explanatory power beyond structural characteristics.

Taken together, these findings support the view that preparedness cannot be reduced to awareness or exposure alone, but emerges from the interaction of resources, experience, and perceived ability to act (Bubeck et al., 2012; Wachinger et al., 2013).

4.2 The preparedness gap as a practical, not conceptual, problem

The observed preparedness gap is not a measurement artifact but a practical challenge for disaster risk communication. Overestimators are of particular concern: individuals who believe they are already sufficiently prepared are unlikely to prioritize additional measures, even when key resources are missing. In contrast, underestimators may experience elevated concern or anxiety without necessarily converting this into effective action. Both patterns represent forms of inefficiency in preparedness behavior.

This misalignment reinforces a well-established insight from risk and disaster research: risk perception and preparedness behavior do not map onto each other in a linear or predictable way. Higher perceived risk does not automatically translate into preparedness, nor does low concern necessarily indicate vulnerability. Instead, preparedness appears constrained by motivational, capability-related, and implementation barriers that operate independently of awareness alone (Grothmann and Reusswig, 2006; Wachinger et al., 2013).

The implication is straightforward but often overlooked: increasing awareness without addressing the translation of concern into action is unlikely to reduce preparedness gaps in a meaningful way.

4.3 What households are prepared for – and what they are not

The distribution of individual preparedness components indicates differentiated readiness rather than uniformly low preparedness. Items with everyday utility, such as alternative lighting or basic medication stocks, were widely available. In contrast, resources critical for prolonged infrastructure disruptions were far less prevalent, particularly water storage and power-independent information access.

This pattern is consistent with prior findings showing that households preferentially adopt preparedness measures that are easy to integrate into daily routines, while neglecting items perceived as exclusively crisis-specific (Gerhold et al., 2019; Wachinger et al., 2013).

From an operational perspective, these gaps are consequential. Water supply and off-grid communication are among the first constraints to become binding during multi-day power outages or cascading infrastructure failures, limiting household autonomy early in a crisis (Gerhold et al., 2019).

4.4 Why settlement size does not explain preparedness differences here

Contrary to common assumptions, objective preparedness did not differ significantly across municipality-size categories. This finding does not imply that context is irrelevant, but rather that settlement size is too coarse a proxy to capture the mechanisms shaping household preparedness.

Rural households may benefit from greater storage capacity and informal support networks, while urban households often have better access to supplies and information but face space constraints and higher reliance on services. If these advantages and disadvantages counterbalance each other, null effects by settlement size are a plausible outcome.

More importantly, this result challenges preparedness strategies that rely heavily on urban–rural distinctions for targeting interventions. The data suggest that individual-level factors, particularly those related to capability and implementation, are more informative than geographic categories alone (Bubeck et al., 2012; Gerhold et al., 2019).

4.5 Structural factors matter – but only to a point

Sociodemographic variables showed a small to moderate associations with objective preparedness. Age, education, and household income were positively correlated with preparedness in bivariate analyses, and age and educational attainment remained relevant predictors in the multivariable model. These effects are consistent with the idea that material resources, life experience, and stability facilitate the acquisition and maintenance of preparedness supplies (Lindell and Perry, 2012; Paton, 2003).

At the same time, the absence of an association between having children in the household and objective preparedness is notable. Despite potentially higher perceived stakes, households with children were not more prepared in resource terms. This supports earlier observations that heightened concern does not automatically translate into preparedness behavior without enabling conditions and guidance (Wachinger et al., 2013).

Overall, structural factors shape preparedness, but they do not determine it.

4.6 Preparedness depends on perceived operational adequacy, not abstract attitudes

Psychological correlates added substantial explanatory value. Beliefs related to problem-solving capability and personal responsibility were positively associated with objective preparedness, while stronger reliance on authorities was negatively associated with preparedness levels. These patterns are consistent with protective action frameworks emphasizing efficacy beliefs, personalization, and decision processes (Grothmann and Reusswig, 2006; Lindell and Perry, 2012).

Importantly, the multivariable analysis points to a more specific mechanism. The strongest psychological predictor of objective preparedness was the belief that one's own preparation would be sufficient in a real disaster. This suggests that preparedness behavior is linked less to abstract attitudes than to perceived operational adequacy, that is, the belief that existing measures would work under real conditions. Similar distinctions between general attitudes and implementation-oriented beliefs have been emphasized in recent preparedness research (Gowan et al., 2015).

4.7 Trust, information use, and the role of communication channels

Participants reported high trust in emergency organizations such as fire services and emergency medical services, while trust in social media as a crisis information source was low. At the same time, official authorities, warning apps, and traditional media dominated routine crisis information use, with social media used by a substantial minority.

This apparent trust–use split is coherent rather than contradictory. Official channels form the backbone of information seeking, while social media functions as an additional exposure environment that can amplify or distort messages. For preparedness communication, this supports a layered approach: official channels should remain central, but social media cannot be ignored as a dissemination and framing space (Lindell and Perry, 2012; Siegrist and Zingg, 2014).

4.8 From awareness to capability: implications for preparedness practice

Taken together, the findings suggest that preparedness policies should move beyond awareness-based messaging toward capability-oriented, behaviorally specific interventions. Evidence from preparedness and protective action research indicates that actionable guidance, clear sequencing, and low-threshold entry points are more effective than abstract risk communication alone (Gowan et al., 2015; Grothmann and Reusswig, 2006).

Focusing on concrete resource gaps, reducing perceived complexity, and clearly delineating household and institutional responsibilities may therefore represent key levers for improving household preparedness in practice (Gerhold et al., 2021, p. 21).

5 Limitations

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting the findings. First, the study is based on a non-representative, self-selected online sample. Individuals with a general interest in crisis preparedness may therefore be overrepresented, potentially leading to an overestimation of preparedness levels in the general population. The observed preparedness gap may thus represent a conservative estimate.

Second, objective preparedness was assessed using a resource-based index derived from self-reported items. Although item selection was guided by national recommendations and focused on concrete, verifiable resources, self-report bias cannot be fully excluded. Future research could complement survey data with observational or mixed-method approaches.

Third, the cross-sectional design limits causal interpretation. While associations between psychological variables and preparedness were identified, the directionality of these relationships cannot be conclusively determined. Longitudinal designs would be required to assess how preparedness perceptions and resources co-evolve over time.

Finally, the study focused on household-level resources as indicators of preparedness. Behavioral competencies, social dynamics during crises, and institutional support networks were not assessed in detail. These dimensions represent important avenues for future research.

6 Conclusion

This study provides empirical evidence that subjective assessments of preparedness do not reliably reflect actual household preparedness. A substantial proportion of participants either overestimated or underestimated their preparedness, indicating systematic discrepancies between perception and objectively measurable preparedness capacities.

The results further show that objective preparedness is only partly associated with socio-demographic characteristics and prior crisis experience. Psychological factors related to implementation, including perceived self-efficacy, responsibility attribution, and reliance on authorities, exhibited additional associations with objective preparedness. In contrast, indicators related to general risk perception alone showed limited explanatory power.

From a disaster risk science perspective, these findings underscore the relevance of distinguishing between perceived and objective preparedness when assessing household vulnerability. Preparedness appears to depend less on awareness of hazards than on factors that facilitate or hinder the translation of perceived preparedness into concrete action. Future research and disaster risk reduction strategies may benefit from focusing more strongly on these implementation-related mechanisms to support effective household-level preparedness.

References

- BBK (Ed.), 2025. *Vorsorgen für Krisen und Katastrophen, Stand 10/2025*, 1. Auflage. ed. Bundesamt für Bevölkerungsschutz und Katastrophenhilfe, Bonn.
- Boin, A., Lodge, M., 2016. DESIGNING RESILIENT INSTITUTIONS FOR TRANSBOUNDARY CRISIS MANAGEMENT: A TIME FOR PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION. *Public Adm.* 94, 289–298. <https://doi.org/10.1111/padm.12264>
- Bubeck, P., Botzen, W.J.W., Aerts, J.C.J.H., 2012. A Review of Risk Perceptions and Other Factors that Influence Flood Mitigation Behavior. *Risk Anal.* 32, 1481–1495. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1539-6924.2011.01783.x>
- Cutter, S.L., Barnes, L., Berry, M., Burton, C., Evans, E., Tate, E., Webb, J., 2008. A place-based model for understanding community resilience to natural disasters. *Glob. Environ. Change* 18, 598–606. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2008.07.013>
- Gerhold, L., Schuchardt, A., Deutschland (Eds.), 2021. *Definition von Schutzziele für Kritische Infrastrukturen: Forschungsstand, rechtlicher Rahmen und politische Entscheidungsfindung: wissenschaftlicher Abschlussbericht, BBK-Projekt-Nr.: FP 417, Abschlussdatum: 09/2019, Forschung im Bevölkerungsschutz. Bundesamt für Bevölkerungsschutz und Katastrophenhilfe, Bonn.*
- Gerhold, L., Wahl, S., Dombrowsky, W.R., 2019. Risk perception and emergency food preparedness in Germany. *Int. J. Disaster Risk Reduct.* 37, 101183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2019.101183>
- Gowan, M.E., Sloan, J.A., Kirk, R.C., 2015. Prepared for what? addressing the disaster readiness gap beyond preparedness for survival. *BMC Public Health* 15, 1139. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-015-2440-8>
- Grothmann, T., Reusswig, F., 2006. People at Risk of Flooding: Why Some Residents Take Precautionary Action While Others Do Not. *Nat. Hazards* 38, 101–120. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-005-8604-6>
- Helbing, D., 2013. Globally networked risks and how to respond. *Nature* 497, 51–59. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature12047>
- Lacher, S., 2024. Exploring disaster preparedness: a scoping review of adult and continuing education approaches in international civil protection research. *J. Risk Res.* 27, 1273–1289. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13669877.2024.2447252>
- Lindell, M.K., Perry, R.W., 2012. The Protective Action Decision Model: Theoretical Modifications and Additional Evidence. *Risk Anal.* 32, 616–632. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1539-6924.2011.01647.x>
- Mileti, D.S., Fitzpatrick, C., Farhar, B.C., 1992. Fostering Public Preparations for Natural Hazards: Lessons from the Parkfield Earthquake Prediction. *Environ. Sci. Policy Sustain. Dev.* 34, 16–39. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00139157.1992.9931434>
- Norris, F.H., Stevens, S.P., Pfefferbaum, B., Wyche, K.F., Pfefferbaum, R.L., 2008. Community Resilience as a Metaphor, Theory, Set of Capacities, and Strategy for Disaster Readiness. *Am. J. Community Psychol.* 41, 127–150. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10464-007-9156-6>
- OECD, 2025. *Government at a Glance 2025, Government at a Glance*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/0efd0bcd-en>
- Paton, D., 2003. Disaster preparedness: a social-cognitive perspective. *Disaster Prev. Manag. Int. J.* 12, 210–216. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09653560310480686>
- Pescaroli, G., Alexander, D., 2015. A definition of cascading disasters and cascading effects: Going beyond the “toppling dominos” metaphor. *Planet@Risk*.

- Siegrist, M., Zingg, A., 2014. The Role of Public Trust During Pandemics: Implications for Crisis Communication. *Eur. Psychol.* 19, 23–32. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1016-9040/a000169>
- Tierney, K.J., 2002. Facing the Unexpected: Disaster Preparedness and Response in the United States. *Disaster Prev. Manag. Int. J.* 11, 222–222. <https://doi.org/10.1108/dpm.2002.11.3.222.1>
- United Nations Office for Disaster Risk, 2022. Global Assessment Report on Disaster Risk Reduction 2022: Our World at Risk: Transforming Governance for a Resilient Future, 1st ed. ed, Global Assessment Report on Disaster Risk Reduction (GAR) Series. United Nations Publications, Bloomfield.
- Wachinger, G., Renn, O., Begg, C., Kuhlicke, C., 2013. The risk perception paradox--implications for governance and communication of natural hazards. *Risk Anal. Off. Publ. Soc. Risk Anal.* 33, 1049–1065. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1539-6924.2012.01942.x>
- Witte, K., 1992. Putting the fear back into fear appeals: The extended parallel process model. *Commun. Monogr.* 59, 329–349. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03637759209376276>

List of Abbreviations

ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
BBK	Federal Office of Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance (Germany)
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
DSGVO	General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)
EPPM	Extended Parallel Process Model
EU	European Union
EUSurvey	Online-Survey Tool
F	F-statistic (analysis of variance)
KATWARN	Public warning system for emergencies in Germany
M	Mean
N	Sample size (total number of observations)
NINA	Emergency Information App of the Federal Government (Germany)
p	p-value
R ²	Coefficient of Determination
ΔR^2	Change in Explained Variance
SD	Standard Deviation
SE	Standard error
t	t-statistic
β	Standardized Regression Coefficient
ρ	Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient

Tables and Figures

Table 1: Gender distribution of the study sample

Values represent absolute frequencies and percentages of the total sample. (N indicates the number of valid responses)

Gender	N	% of total
Diverse	3	1.1
Male	138	51.9
Female	125	47.0

Table 2: Highest educational attainment of participants

(N indicates the number of valid responses)

Highest educational attainment	N	% of total
No formal qualification	3	1.1
Primary education	4	1.5
Secondary school (lower)	21	7.9
Upper secondary qualification	84	31.7
Vocational training	36	13.6
University degree	117	44.2

Table 3: Household net income distribution

(N indicates the number of valid responses)

Household net income	N	% of total
No information	14	5.3
< €1,000	10	3.8
€1,001 – €2,000	37	14.1
€2,001 – €3,000	45	17.1
€3,001 – €4,000	38	14.4
€4,001 – €5,000	32	12.2
> €5,000	87	33.1

Table 4: Municipality size of participants' place of residence, classified by population size

(N indicates the number of valid responses)

Municipality size	N	% of total
Rural area (<5,000 inhabitants)	70	26.4
Small town (5,000–20,000 inhabitants)	51	19.2
Medium-sized city (20,000–100,000 inhabitants)	46	17.4
Large city (>100,000 inhabitants)	98	37.0

Table 5: Subjective assessment of crisis likelihood and self-reported preparedness for selected crisis scenarios. Responses were recorded on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree); N indicates the number of valid responses; SD = standard deviation.

Item	N (%)	Mean (\pmSD)
I would be well prepared for a major crisis.	260 (97.7)	2.87 (\pm 1.01)
I consider a prolonged power outage to be likely.	261 (98.1)	3.35 (\pm 1.13)
I am well prepared for a prolonged power outage.	261 (98.1)	2.72 (\pm 1.12)
I consider natural disasters (e.g., floods, storms) in my region to be likely.	261 (98.1)	3.16 (\pm 1.19)
I am well prepared for a natural disaster.	261 (98.1)	2.60 (\pm 1.01)
I consider long-term supply disruptions to be possible.	262 (98.5)	2.62 (\pm 1.12)
I am well prepared for supply disruptions.	262 (98.5)	2.62 (\pm 1.09)
I consider another pandemic or major health crisis to be likely.	260 (97.7)	3.66 (\pm 1.13)
I am well prepared for a health crisis.	260 (97.7)	2.99 (\pm 1.01)

Table 6: Psychological and attitudinal items related to individual crisis preparedness.

Responses were recorded on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree); N indicates the number of valid responses; SD = standard deviation.

Item	N (%)	Mean (\pmSD)
I believe that I can remain capable of acting in a crisis.	266 (100)	3.71(\pm 1.11)
Even in difficult situations, I find ways to solve problems.	266 (100)	3.94 (\pm 1.07)
I am confident that I can protect my household in an emergency.	266 (100)	3.15 (\pm 1.12)
Disasters usually affect others, not me.	266 (100)	2.29 (\pm 1.24)
I assume that no major crises will occur in my region.	266 (100)	2.47 (\pm 1.18)
It is my responsibility to be prepared for crises.	266 (100)	3.73 (\pm 1.24)
I rely on authorities and organizations to manage crises.	266 (100)	2.36 (\pm 1.18)
I trust that the state will provide sufficient protection in case of war or defense.	262 (98.5)	2.47 (\pm 1.11)

Table 7: Social resources, planning behavior, and information-related items in the context of crisis preparedness.

Responses were recorded on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree); N indicates the number of valid responses; SD = standard deviation.

Item	N (%)	Mean (\pmSD)
I have thought about where I would go or evacuate to in an emergency.	261 (98.1)	2.57 (\pm 1.32)
I have taken concrete precautions (e.g., shelter, emergency backpack).	259 (97.4)	1.60 (\pm 1.01)
I could rely on help from my neighbors in an emergency.	261 (98.1)	3.08 (\pm 1.32)
I know neighbors who would help me in an emergency.	259 (97.4)	3.38 (\pm 1.29)
I would help others if they needed support in a crisis.	262 (98.5)	4.26 (\pm 0.89)
In my circle of friends or family, there are well prepared.	259 (100)	2.98 (\pm 1.13)
I exchange information about crisis preparedness with others.	262 (98.5)	2.47 (\pm 1.34)
I frequently think about possible crises or disasters in everyday life.	260 (97.7)	2.94 (\pm 1.28)

Table 8: Frequencies of household-level preparedness resources used to construct the objective preparedness index

(Selection based on national recommendations, N indicates the number of valid responses).

Resource	Yes N (%)	No N (%)
Non-perishable food sufficient for at least 3 days	216 (81.2)	50 (18.8)
At least 2 liters of water per person per day for 3 days	165 (62.3)	100 (37.7%)
Household emergency medical kit (incl. personal medication)	239 (90.2)	26 (9.8)
Alternative light source (e.g., flashlight, candles)	255 (96.6)	9 (3.4)
Power bank or alternative phone charging option	208 (78.8)	56 (21.2)
Radio operable without mains power (hand driven)	106 (40.0)	159 (60.0)
First aid course attended within the last 5 years	206 (77.4)	60 (22.6)
Packed emergency bag for rapid evacuation	238 (89.5)	28 (10.5)
Important documents readily accessible	189 (71.9)	74 (28.1)
Insurance coverage or financial reserves for crises	146 (54.9)	120 (45.1)
Camping stove or alternative cooking option	152 (57.4)	113 (42.6)

Table 9: Reported reasons for insufficient household preparedness.

Counts and percentages refer to the total sample. Multiple selections were allowed. (N indicates the number of valid responses).

Reason	N	% of total
“I do not know where to start.”	75	28.2
“I think nothing serious will happen anyway.”	28	10.5
“I do not have enough time.”	60	22.6
“I cannot afford it.”	75	28.2
“I have not thought about it yet.”	80	30.1